

**PECULIARITIES OF EXTERNAL APICAL ROOT RESORPTION ASSOCIATED WITH
ORTHODONTIC TOOTH MOVEMENT IN ROOTS OF VARYING APICAL MORPHOLOGY AND
ITS QUANTITATIVE AND QUALITATIVE SYSTEMATIZATION**

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Abstract

Apical root resorption is an adverse consequence frequently observed in orthodontic treatment, resulting in the irreversible loss of dental structure. The clinical diagnosis of this condition primarily relies on routine radiographic assessments, including periapical and panoramic radiographs (Dudic A. et al, 2009). The sagittal section allows visualization distinctly of the resorption lesions on the labial and lingual surfaces of the root. Our objective was to assess, the quantitative and qualitative rates of tooth root apical resorption resulting from orthodontic treatment and to investigate the correlation between root morphology and the configuration of the resorption lesions. The examination of 46 resorbed teeth revealed various types of resorption. The introduction of three-dimensional imaging has introduced the possibility of an accurate quantitative evaluation, allowing for the differentiation of root resorption levels across various root surfaces, which is a preventive measure to prevent distant root resorption and tooth loss in the process of orthodontic treatment.

Keywords: orthodontic forces, apical root resorption, tooth root morphology, sagittal CBCT images.

Introduction

Clinically, orthodontic root resorption is typically asymptomatic and lacks noticeable signs unless it reaches an advanced stage, at which point significant tooth mobility may occur (Abbott PV, 2022).

The clinical manifestations of orthodontic root resorption are often obscured by the stabilizing effect of orthodontic archwires and the routine discomfort associated with orthodontic treatment. Additionally, clinicians generally anticipate a certain degree of increased tooth mobility during active orthodontic therapy, which may result in the unnoticed progression of resorption-related mobility. Early signs of orthodontic root resorption may be observed if concurrent pulp pathosis occurs due to incidental factors, such as dental trauma. However, orthodontic resorption itself does not induce pulp pathosis. The diagnosis of orthodontic root resorption is typically made when radiographic imaging is performed during orthodontic treatment to evaluate treatment progress or upon obtaining post-treatment radiographs. Radiographic imaging may also be performed in cases of increased tooth mobility and tenderness during orthodontic treatment or when persistent mobility is observed following the removal of orthodontic appliances (Paul V et al, 2022).

Radiographically, the roots exhibit shortening and blunting with rounded apices. The lamina dura typically appears intact, while the periodontal ligament (PDL) space may remain normal or appear widened, primarily due to orthodontic tooth movement rather than the resorptive process itself. There are no indications of ankylosis, nor is there any evidence of periapical radiolucency or radiopacity. The apical foramen

typically remains open, lacking an apical constriction, due to the shortening of the tooth root (Abbott PV, 2022). The apical foramen may gradually narrow over time as the pulp generates secondary dentin through its normal physiological processes, particularly as the patient ages.

The management of orthodontic root resorption depends on the timing of its diagnosis. If identified during orthodontic treatment, intervention may involve discontinuing treatment or reducing the forces applied to the affected teeth. However, reducing orthodontic forces does not guarantee the cessation of the resorptive process. The decision to discontinue orthodontic treatment requires careful consideration, as the teeth may not be in a stable occlusal relationship or may not be positioned aesthetically. In such cases, a modified treatment plan with adjusted, compromised, or reduced expectations may be necessary.

If orthodontic root resorption is diagnosed after the completion of orthodontic treatment (e.g., on post-treatment radiographs), the resorption is unlikely to progress further, as orthodontic forces are no longer being applied to the affected tooth/teeth. However, regular monitoring through follow-up radiographs (e.g., after six months) should be scheduled to confirm that the resorption has ceased. Additionally, this monitoring will assess whether tooth mobility has decreased, ensure the health of the pulp, periapical, and periodontal tissues, and verify that the patient is maintaining optimal oral hygiene. The prognosis of teeth with orthodontic resorption depends largely on how much resorption has occurred—that is, how short the tooth roots have become (4). The initial radiographic signs of resorption

typically become evident within 6 to 9 months after the commencement of treatment. Since the resorptive process is asymptomatic, radiological screening during this period is recommended for patients undergoing orthodontic treatment (Marcio Jose da Silva, 2013).

Regrettably, the various classifications of tooth resorption in the literature have not adhered to fundamental classification principles. Additionally, there is a lack of consistency among the numerous classifications, with many different terms being used to describe the same type of resorption (Paul V. et al, 2022).

An attempt was made to employ an etiological approach in nine of the sixteen classifications identified in a narrative review by Aidos et al (Aidos H, et al, 2018). Examples of these include the classifications by Fuss et al. (Fuss Z. et al, 2003, Lindskog SF et al, 2006, Heithersay GS, 2007, Santos B et al, 2011, Darcey J et al, 2013, Sak M, et al, 2016). Other classifications have integrated the etiological approach with factors such as trauma, the location, and the type of resorption, or have exclusively specified trauma as the etiology (Kanas RJ,

et al, 2011). During orthodontic treatment, four anatomical structures are affected: bone, periodontal ligament, pulp, and cementum, all of which are influenced by the forces exerted by orthodontic appliances. Surface resorption is a natural occurrence during orthodontic treatment, resulting from the movement of the teeth throughout the treatment period. It is evident that dentin remains unaffected by osteoclasts and the resorption process is controlled until the cementum is repaired (Andreasen JO, et al, 2007).

Levander and Malmgren proposed a classification system for the different types of apical external resorption based on the degree of severity. They distinguished four levels: • Level 1: the resorption is minimal and simply leaves an irregular apical root contour. • Level 2 (minor resorption): the resorption lesion is no greater than 2 mm on the hard tissues. Level 3 (severe resorption): the resorption destroys up to the first third of the root. • Level 4 (extreme resorption): the resorption extends beyond the first third of the root length (Levander E, et al, 1988) (Fig.1).

Figure 1. 1-Irregular root contour, opened apex. 2- Resorption less than 2 mm 3- Resorption more than 2 mm up to one-third root level. 4- Severe resorption over one-third root level (Levander E, et al, 1988).

Marcio Jose da Silva Campos et al created a qualitative visual scale for classifying the sagittal appearance of the apical root resorption lesions (Fig. 2.) (Marcio Jose da Silva Campos, et al, 2013).

Fig 2. The visual scale representing the classifications of apical root resorption of the incisors in sagittal cuts: type 1, flat apical root resorption; type 2, flat apical root resorption associated with superficial resorption on the lingual surface; type 3, flat apical root resorption associated with superficial resorption on the labial surface; type 4, apical root resorption associated with superficial resorption on the labial and lingual surfaces; type 5, diagonal apical root resorption in the labiolingual direction; type 6, diagonal apical root resorption in the lingual-labial direction.

Objectives:

Our study aims to assess, the quantitative and qualitative rates of tooth roots apical resorption resulting from orthodontic treatment and to investigate the correlation between root morphology and the configuration of the resorption lesions.

Materials and Methods:

This study included sagittal CBCT images of 46 resorbed anterior and posterior tooth roots examined in

40 patients with non-removable appliances. In order to assess the quantitative rates of apical root resorption we used the classification of Levander and Malmgren (1988).

The degree of root resorption was calculated by the difference in the tooth length between the pre and post-treatment measurements using 2-dimensional radiographs (Fig. 1, Fig.2).

Figure 1. Panoramic X-ray shows the degree of root apical resorption after 12 months of treatment.

Figure 2. Panoramic X-ray shows the degree of root apical resorption after 6 months of treatment.

For the qualitative evaluation of resorbed lesions qualitative visual scale was applied (Marcio Jose da Silva Campos, et al, 2013). The lengths of the labial and lingual surfaces of the roots diagnosed with apical root resorption were compared with the longest root length. The sagittal image selected for the analysis of each root was obtained from the sagittal section at the mesiodistal center of the root, perpendicular to the incisal edge. Three reference points were identified: L, the most apical point on the labial surface of the root where apical root resorption initiates; Li, the most apical point on the lingual surface of the root where apical root resorption commences; and A, the most apical point of the tooth root. A horizontal line was constructed through the midpoint of the labial and lingual cemento-enamel junctions, oriented perpendicularly to the long axis of the

tooth root. The lengths of the labial and lingual surfaces were ascertained by measuring the distance between points L and Li, along with their respective orthogonal projections onto the cemento-enamel line. Similarly, the maximum root length was measured as the distance between point A and its orthogonal projection onto the cemento-enamel line. (Fig. 3). The shortest root length was determined by the measurement of the shorter dimension between the labial and lingual root surfaces. The type of resorption was detected according to the length of the labial and lingual surfaces: L and $Li = LRL$ correspond to the type 1 visual scale. $Li < LRL$ corresponds to the types 2 and 5 of the visual scale. $L < LRL$ corresponds to the types 3 and 6 of the visual scale. L and $Li < LRL$ corresponds to the type 4 of visual scale.

Figure 3. The sagittal cut of the maxillary incisor shows points L, Li, and A, and their respective orthogonal projections on the cemento-enamel line.

The Results:

The study results were processed statistically. The lengths of the labial and lingual surfaces of 46 tooth roots diagnosed with apical root resorption resulting from orthodontic treatment in sagittal CBCT images

were analyzed to investigate the correlation between root morphology and the configuration of the resorption lesions using a qualitative visual scale. The data obtained from the study results were processed statistically: Descriptive statistics- mean, standard deviation,

and standard error were used. Relative risk was calculated. Comparisons between groups were made using the Student's t-test. Were used a 95% confidence interval.

The distributions of the resorbed roots of different morphology, assessed based on the amount of root loss is demonstrated in Table 1.

Table 1.

Distribution of the Varying Apical Morphology roots resorption according to the severity of resorbed lessons.

Apical morphology	Number of cases	Degree 1	Degree 2	Degree3	Degree 4
Pipette-shaped	3	-	1	2	-
Shortened	5	-	1	-	3
Bent	15	1	9	5	-
Pointed	8	-	-	5	3
Normal	15	2	4	7	2

The distributions of the resorbed roots of different morphology, assessed based on the lengths of the labial

and lingual surfaces and their correlations with the visual scale used to classify apical root resorption in sagittal sections are presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

Distribution of the Varying Apical Morphology roots resorption according to the length of the labial and lingual surfaces.

Apical morphology	Number of cases	Type 1	Type 2	Type 3	Type 4	Type 5	Type 6
Pipette-shaped	3	1	-	-	1	-	1
Shortened	5	1	-	-	4	-	-
Bent	15	3	-	-	3	9	-
Pointed	8	6	-	-	2	-	-
Normal	15	6	-	-	9	-	-

A sagittal section examination of 46 resorbed teeth revealed various types of resorption (Fig,4,5,6,7,8).

Fig 4. The maxillary molar labial mesial root with a bent apical morphology illustrates the resorption lesion that belongs to Type 5 (A -before treatment, B, C-after treatment-coronal and sagittal sections)

Fig 5. The mandibular molar distal root with a shortened apical morphology illustrates the resorption lesion that belongs to Type 4. (A -before treatment, B, C-after treatment-coronal and sagittal sections)

Fig 6. The maxillary canine root with a pointed apical morphology illustrates the resorption lesion that belongs to Type 4. (A -before treatment, B, C-after treatment-coronal and sagittal sections)

Fig 7. The mandibular canine root with a pipette-shaped apical morphology illustrates the resorption lesion that belongs to Type 6. (A -before treatment, B, C-after treatment-coronal and sagittal sections)

Fig 8. The maxillary central incisor root with normal apical morphology illustrates the resorption lesion that belongs to Type 1. (A -before treatment, B, after treatment (coronal and sagittal sections))

Conclusions

Regarding the quantitative assessment of resorbed lesions, out of the 46 examined resorbed roots, two exhibited aberrations in apical morphology. Resorption up to 2 mm was observed in 15 cases, while 19 roots demonstrated resorption ranging from 2 mm to one-third of the total root length. Severe resorption, characterized by a loss exceeding one-third of the root length, was identified in only eight cases.

According to the qualitative visual scale, out of the 46 investigated resorbed roots, 17 were classified as Type 1 resorption and 19 as Type 4. Among these 36 cases, the root morphologies observed included pipette-shaped, shortened, normal, bent, and pointed forms. Only one root with a pipette-shaped apical morphology exhibited Type 6 resorption. Among the 15 roots with bent apical morphology, only 9 exhibited Type 6 resorption. No evidence of Type 2 or Type 3 resorption was identified.

Obtained Results and Discussion

All root resorption occurs in three dimensions, and its two-dimensional radiographic evaluation lacks geometric accuracy, leading to questionable estimates of the lesion's extent (Marcio Jose da Silva et al, 2013). When apical root resorption is assessed using periapical or panoramic radiographs, the image displays the superimposition of all root structures in the labiolingual direction. Unlike the classification developed by Malmgren et al., which quantitatively classified apical root resorption lesions in periapical radiographic images, the qualitative scale visually represents the extent to which root resorption has affected the labial and lingual surfaces of the periapical region. Therefore, apical root resorption should be assessed using a CBCT method that enables differentiation across each root surface, as these surfaces may be affected in distinct ways. The sagittal section allows visualization distinctly of the resorption lesions on the labial and lingual surfaces of the root. Regarding the involvement of the labial and lingual surfaces by apical root resorption lesions, no statistically significant difference was observed between the lengths of these two surfaces, indicating that root resorption associated with orthodontic treatment has affected both surfaces equally, but the labial and lingual surfaces are affected in different degrees; According to our results from the point of view of the qualitative evaluation of resorption roots with different root morphology are more susceptible to flat apical root resorption (Type 1) and apical root resorption associated with superficial resorption on the labial and lingual surfaces (Type 4). Regarding the severity of resorbed lesions, the majority of cases (19 roots) with varying root morphology exhibited resorption ranging from 2 mm to one-third of the total root length.

The introduction of three-dimensional imaging has introduced the possibility of an accurate quantitative evaluation, allowing for the differentiation of root

resorption levels across various root surfaces, which is a preventive measure to prevent distant root resorption and tooth loss in the process of orthodontic treatment.

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